

NOTES

TABLE 2—BIOLOGICAL SCREENING RESULTS OF ALKYLARYLAMINOACETYL-2-AMINOTHIAZOLES AND ALKYLARYLAMINOACETYL-2-AMINOENZIMIDAZOLES AS LOCAL ANAESTHETIC

Compound No.	Surface anaesthesia			Infiltration anaesthesia			Conduction anaesthesia			
	Conc. of drug (%)	Intensity	Duration (min)	Conc. of drug (%)	Intensity	Duration (min)	Conc. of drug (%)	Onset of anaesthesia (min) in HCl of strength		
								0.5 N	0.1 N	0.2 N
1.	2	complete	3	0.2	nil	—	0.2	20	21	21
2.	2	nil	—	0.2	partial	8	—	—	—	—
3.	—	—	—	—	complete	10	0.2	18	19	19
4.	2.5	partial	8	0.2	complete	15	0.2	8	9	10
5.	2	complete	10	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
6.	2	complete	14	0.2	nil	—	0.2	15	16	17
7.	2	partial	6	0.2	nil	—	0.2	20	20	21
8.	2.5	complete	8	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
9.	2	nil	—	0.2	complete	9	0.2	23	24	24
10.	2	complete	22	0.2	complete	16	0.2	9	10	10
11.	2	complete	18	0.2	partial	5	0.2	13	15	16
12.	—	—	—	0.25	complete	7	—	—	—	—
13.	2	partial	12	0.2	complete	12	0.2	10	11	12
14.	2.5	complete	14	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
15.	2	nil	—	0.2	complete	8	0.2	5	6	7
16.	2	complete	4	0.2	nil	—	0.2	17	18	19
17.	2	partial	4	0.2	complete	3	0.2	20	22	22
18.	2.5	complete	5	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
19.	2	complete	7	0.2	nil	—	0.2	9	10	10
20.	2	nil	—	0.1	nil	—	0.2	19	20	20
Procaine hydrochloride (Standard)	2	—	—	0.2	nil	—	—	—	—	—
	2	partial	2	0.1	partial	4	0.2	27	29	29
	2.5	complete	4	0.2	complete	6	—	—	—	—
	2	complete	8	0.2	complete	5	0.2	31	32	33
	2	complete	20	0.2	complete	37	0.2	7	8	8
	2	complete	19	0.2	complete	20	0.2	10	11	12
	2	complete	13	0.1	partial	10	0.2	12	13	13
	2.5	complete	15	0.2	complete	12	—	—	—	—
	2	complete	10	0.2	complete	10	0.2	16	17	17
	2	complete	15	0.2	complete	12	0.2	15	16	17

maximum activity with duration of infiltration anaesthesia on frog. Compounds no 7, 8, 17 and 18 were found to be more active than the standard drug when tested as surface anaesthetic. In comparison to the standard drug, the compounds no. 4 and 20 were found to be equally active, compounds no. 1, 2, 5, 6, 11, 12 and 14 slightly more active and compounds no. 15 and 16 were observed to be most active.

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Studies on Antitubercular Agents. Part-III : Preparation of Some *p*-(2,4-Diaryl-amino-6-S-Triazinylamino)-Benzaldehyde/ Acetophenone Thiosemicarbazones as Potential Tuberculostatic Agents

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LITERATURE reveals that a number of studies have been carried out on the antileprotic and antitubercular activity of thiosemicarba-

zones^{1-8,17,18}. The thiosemicarbazones of aromatic aldehydes in general possess potential drug activity. The study of structure-activity relationship suggests that the presence of substituent in benzene ring increases the *in vitro* tuberculostatic activity but only *p*-substituted benzaldehyde thiosemicarbazones have significant *in vivo* activity⁹⁻¹⁶. Further, *s*-triazine derivatives have wide spectrum of biological activity¹⁹⁻²⁷. It was therefore thought that incorporation of 2,4-diarylamino-6-*s*-triazinyl moiety into *p*-aminobenzaldehyde/acetophenone thiosemicarbazones might modify their tuberculostatic activity.

The synthetic sequence of the title compounds is outlined in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

Experimental

Preparation of 2,4-diarylamino-6-chloro-*s*-triazine(II): These were prepared by reported method²⁰⁻²¹.

Preparation of p-(2,4-diarylamino-6-*s*-triazinyl-amino)-acetophenone (III): To a solution of *p*-aminoacetophenone (0.01 mole) in dioxane (10 ml) was added a solution of appropriate II (0.01 mole) in dioxane (15 ml) at 80°. The solution heated at 85-90° for 2 hr with the simultaneous addition of NaOH (aqueous 10%; 4 ml) and poured on water, filtered, washed with water, dried and recrystallised from ethanol (95%).

Preparation of 2,4-diarylamino-6-(4-carbomethoxyanilino)-*s*-triazine(IV): Methyl-*p*-aminobenzoate (0.015 mole) and appropriate II (0.015 mole) were separately dissolved in dioxane (25 ml) and mixed at 80°. The solution refluxed for 2 hr with the

simultaneous dropwise addition of NaOH (aqueous 10%; 6 ml), the contents poured on ice, filtered, washed repeatedly with water and recrystallised from ethanol (95%).

Preparation of p-(2,4-diarylamino-6-*s*-triazinyl-amino)-benzoyl p-toluenesulfonyl hydrazide (V): The ethanolic solution of IV (0.012 mole) and *p*-toluenesulfonylhydrazide (0.0122 mole) was refluxed for 3.5 hr and allowed to cool to room temperature (25°) and filtered. The product so obtained was washed with boiling water and recrystallised from ethanol (95%). The ir spectra of V show strong bands in the 1180-1150, 1340-1305 cm⁻¹ regions.

Preparation of p-(2,4-diarylamino-6-*s*-triazinyl-amino)-benzaldehyde thiosemicarbazone (VI): Thiosemicarbazide (0.01 mole) and appropriate V (0.008 mole) were dissolved in a mixture of ethylene glycol and water (3 : 1) containing NaOH (10%; 10 ml). The solution heated at 90-95° for 2.5 hr and poured on ice, rendered acidic with 1 N HCl, filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from ethanol (95%).

Preparation of p-(2,4-diarylamino-6-*s*-triazinyl-amino)-acetophenone thiosemicarbazones(VII): Usual condensation of thiosemicarbazide and III in EtOH furnished VII which were recrystallised from ethanol (95%).

The physical data of the compounds are recorded in Tables 1 and 2. The ir spectra of VI and VII show strong bands in the 1660-1630, 1500-1470, 1380-1360 and 1220-1205 cm⁻¹ regions.

Antimycobacterial activity: The antimycobacterial activity of the compounds was studied *in vitro* by two fold serial dilution method against H_{87R} strain of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* using Lowenstein-Jensen's egg medium. MIC (Table 2)

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF THE 2,4-DIARYLAMINO-6-CHLORO/SUBSTITUTED ANILINO-S-TRIAZINES (II, III, IV AND V)

Ar	Type of compound	% Yield	m.p. °C	Type of compound	% Yield	m.p. °C
Phenyl	II	88.7	197 ²⁰	IV	97.6	184
<i>p</i> -Tolyl	II	93.1	197 ²⁰	IV	99.1	202
<i>p</i> -Anisyl	II	93.4	202 ²¹	IV	96.0	205
<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	I	90.9	222-23 ²¹	IV	98.4	194
<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	II	94.8	240-41	IV	96.5	199
<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	II	94.7	304 ²⁰	IV	95.6	222-23
<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	II	92.2	296-97	I	97.0	214
<i>m</i> -Tolyl	II	93.4	144 ²⁰	IV	98.6	198
<i>o</i> -Tolyl	II	90.9	164 ²⁰	IV	97.5	198
<i>o</i> -Tolyl	III	97.2	209	V	50.7	293
<i>m</i> -Tolyl	III	95.1	214	V	54.0	296
<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	I	90.8	263	V	44.1	284
<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	III	93.2	298	V	43.9	385(d)
<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	II	94.6	273	V	47.7	281
<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	I	93.1	238	V	49.6	293
<i>p</i> -Anisyl	III	96.9	242	V	57.2	304
<i>p</i> -Tolyl	III	95.1	214	V	56.2	237
Phenyl	III	96.5	216	V	55.0	298

All the above compounds gave satisfactory C, N and S analyses.

TABLE 2—DATA OF THE THIOSEMICARBAZONES VI AND VII

Ar	R	% Yield	m.p. °C	MIC µg/ml
C ₆ H ₅ -	H	48.4	236	8
C ₆ H ₅ -	CH ₃	66.6	311	64
p-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	H	48.7	231	8
p-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	CH ₃	68.8	298	64
p-OH ₃ O-C ₆ H ₄ -	H	48.2	248	8
p-CH ₃ O-C ₆ H ₄ -	CH ₃	78.2	265	64
p-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	H	48.1	238	8
p-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	CH ₃	76.9	275	64
p-Br-C ₆ H ₄ -	H	42.1	298(d)	16
p-Br-C ₆ H ₄ -	CH ₃	77.1	302	-
p-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	H	42.6	245	-
p-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	CH ₃	77.6	336	-
m-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	H	49.8	219-20	8
m-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	CH ₃	74.9	283	32
m-H ₃ C-C ₆ H ₄ -	H	48.0	230-31	8
m-H ₃ C-C ₆ H ₄ -	CH ₃	66.5	294	32
o-H ₃ C-C ₆ H ₄ -	H	50.7	238	8
o-H ₃ C-C ₆ H ₄ -	CH ₃	69.3	288	32

All the above compounds gave satisfactory C, N and S analyses.

is the minimum concentration which inhibits almost completely the growth of the test bacterium.

It is evident from the experimental data (Table 2) that *p*-(2,4-diarylamino-6-s-triazinyl-amino)-benzaldehyde thiosemicarbazones (VI) have higher tuberculostatic activity than the corresponding acetophenone thiosemicarbazone analogues (VII). The intermediate compounds II-V do not possess any significant activity against *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* reflecting on the key role of thiosemicarbazone moiety in the antimycobacterial activity of the title compounds.

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Studies on Antitubercular Agents. Preparation of 2-Arylamino-4-(4-Carboethoxyanilino)-6-Isonicotinylhydrazino-1,3,5-Triazine

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LITERATURE reveals that a number of studies has been carried out on the chemotherapeutic potentialities of 1,3,5-triazine derivatives. It was thought that incorporation of substituted amino-1,3,5-triazine moiety into the tuberculostatic agent isonicotinic acid hydrazide, might modify the biological activities. Thus, 2,4,6-trichloro-1,3,5-triazine and ethyl *p*-aminobenzoate were reacted to produce 2-(4-carboethoxyanilino)-4,6-dichloro-1,3,5-triazine, which on reaction with isonicotinic acid hydrazide and subsequently with different aromatic amines gave 2-arylamino-4-(4-carboethoxyanilino)-6-isonicotinylhydrazino-1,3,5-triazine¹⁻⁴.

2-arylamino-4-(4-carboethoxyanilino)-6-isonicotinylhydrazino-1,3,5-triazine.